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Terdkiad Nontapot & Kuo Chieh Chao

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Advancing rainfall-induced landslide hazard mapping: comparative study of semi-quantitative, statistical, hybrid, and deterministic models

Terdkiad Nontapot and Kuo Chieh Chao

Department of Civil and Infrastructure Engineering, Asian Institute of Technology, Bangkok, Thailand

ABSTRACT

Landslide hazard mapping is crucial for risk assessment, land-use planning, and disaster mitigation, especially in regions prone to rainfall-induced slope failures. This study compares five landslide hazard mapping approaches: Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Frequency Ratio (FR), Logistic Regression (LR), AHP + FR + Penalty LR hybrid, and TRIGRS methods, applied to the Ardi Watershed, Thailand. Model performance was assessed based on methodology, data requirements, and predictive accuracy, using AUC, TPR, FPR, precision, and F1. TRIGRS showed the highest performance (AUC = 88.97%, TPR = 61%, FPR = 11%, precision = 67%, F1 = 64%), effectively modelling rainfall infiltration and slope instability. The AHP + FR + Penalty LR hybrid also performed well (AUC = 81.53%, TPR = 67%, FPR = 29%, precision = 23%, F1 = 34%), combining expert judgment with statistic. Standalone, the AHP, FR, and LR yielded lower accuracy (AUC = 68.03%–70.57%), and are suitable for preliminary or data-limited assessments. The study emphasizes the importance of rainfall classification and proper zonation techniques for producing a Landslide Hazard Map. Overall, findings underscore the need to choose hazard mapping methods tailored to local data availability and triggering factors. The study concludes with method-specific recommendations and the importance of modelling frameworks, particularly under climate change.

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Introduction

Rainfall-induced landslides are among the most challenging natural hazards that commonly occur after intense rainfall in mountainous and hilly regions. It is also one of the most devastating, posing significant threats to human lives, infrastructure, and the environment (Ng and Shi 1998). In many parts of Southeast Asia, including northern Thailand, landslides are frequently triggered by intense rainfall events, which accelerate slope instability, particularly in geologically sensitive areas (Jaboyedoff 2012; Chao et al. 2018; Zhao 2024; Gaviola et al. 2025). As climate change is expected to increase the frequency of intense rainfall (IPCC 2021), the incidence of landslides is also projected to rise. Consequently, gaining a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms that cause landslides in specific regions is crucial. Accurate prediction and mapping of landslide hazards are crucial for disaster preparedness, land-use planning, and the development of early warning systems (Guzzetti et al. 2006).

Various methodologies have been developed to assess and map landslide hazards, each with differing levels of complexity, data requirements, and predictive performance. These include semi-quantitative approaches based on expert knowledge, statistical models that rely on historical landslide data, physically based models that simulate the underlying mechanics of slope failure, and the combined approach of the above methods (Van Westen et al. 2008). The most widely used techniques are the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method, the Frequency Ratio (FR) method, the Logistic Regression (LR) method, and the Transient Rainfall Infiltration and Grid-Based Regional Slope-Stability Analysis (TRIGRS) method (Ayalew and Yamagishi 2005; Baum et al. 2008; Yilmaz 2009; Ciurleo et al. 2019). Each method offers unique strengths and limitations depending on the availability of spatial, geological, and hydrological data,

CONTACT Terdkiad Nontapot n.terdkiad@gmail.com

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as well as the scale of application. Many studies have compared the performance of different landslide hazard mapping techniques mentioned above (Yilmaz 2009; Mandal and Mondal 2019). However, the integration of these approaches to improve mapping accuracy has received limited scholarly attention. In particular, comparative investigations in Thailand remain scarce, despite the country's complex geomorphological and geological settings and the uneven availability of data.

This study presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of these five approaches, including the AHP, FR, LR, AHP + FR + Penalty LR, and TRIGRS methods, using the Ardi Watershed in northern Thailand as the case study. The objective is to evaluate and contrast each method's performance, accuracy, and practical applicability in generating landslide hazard maps under data-rich and data-limited conditions. Field investigations, geotechnical laboratory tests, satellite imagery, and a well-documented landslide inventory were used to support model development. In addition, rainfall-induced landslides from the September 8, 2020, storm event served as a critical benchmark for model validation.

The landslide hazard maps generated using these five approaches were evaluated using the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis, True Positive Rate (TPR) or Sensitivity, False Positive Rate (FPR), precision, and F1 score providing a quantitative measure of the predictive capability of each model. This comparative framework not only highlights the most effective approaches for landslide hazard assessment in the study area but also offers practical insights for selecting appropriate modeling techniques in other regions with similar geomorphological and data conditions.

The study begins with a review of relevant landslide hazard mapping techniques, classifying them into semi-quantitative, statistical, hybrid, and deterministic approaches, and outlining their theoretical foundations and limitations. This is followed by a description of the study area, including geological, geomorphological, and climatic characteristics, as well as field investigations and laboratory testing used to generate input data. The methodology section details the implementation of five hazard mapping models (AHP, FR, LR, AHP + FR + Penalty LR, and TRIGRS) and explains the procedures for rainfall classification, zonation, and model validation. The results section presents the landslide hazard maps, model performance metrics, and comparative outcomes across the different approaches. The discussion section interprets these findings by highlighting methodological contrasts, data requirements, and predictive accuracy, with particular reference to their applicability in Thailand. Finally, the conclusions and recommendations section synthesizes the key insights, emphasizing the strengths, limitations, and practical implications of each method for hazard assessment and risk management.

Review of landslide hazard mapping techniques

Various techniques have been developed to assess landslide hazard mapping, each with distinct methodologies, data requirements, and predictive capabilities. These mapping approaches can generally be classified into four categories, including (1) semi-quantitative (expert-based) approach, (2) statistical (data-driven) approach, (3) semi-quantitative and statistical hybrid (expert + statistical) approach, and (4) deterministic (physically-based) approach. This section provides an overview of commonly used methods in these techniques, highlighting their theoretical foundations, common applications, strengths, and limitations in landslide hazard mapping.

Semi-quantitative approach

The semi-quantitative (expert-based) approach assesses areas prone to failure by analyzing fundamental factors such as geomorphological characteristics, topography, water channels, slope, and historical landslide occurrences. This method is because the chance of landslide occurrence is higher when a location has the same factors. Recently, the expert-based approach has developed more on the quantitative analysis and can provide a meaningful quantitative value for landslide probabilistic (Dahal et al. 2007; Muthu and Petrou 2007; Bryce 2024).

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is one of the widely used semi-quantitative methods that applies systematic decision-making to landslide mapping. It is particularly effective in regions with limited

landslide inventory data, enabling decision-makers to evaluate the relative importance of multiple conditioning factors systematically. For landslide mapping using the AHP, several studies have successfully applied this method to assess landslide susceptibility in different regions. The studies utilized the AHP to map landslide susceptibility, incorporating factors like slope, aspect, drainage density, and land use to create a comprehensive landslide susceptibility map (Hasekiogulları and Ercanoglu 2012; El Jazouli et al. 2019; Mandal and Mondal 2019).

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) combines mathematical calculations with expert judgments to evaluate the relative importance of various factors affecting landslide hazard. The process involves structuring the problem hierarchically, comparing criteria pairwise, and assigning weights. Pairwise comparisons are conducted between all factors using Saaty's nine-point scale (refer to Table 1) to reflect their relative importance in contributing to landslide occurrence (Saaty 2008). The resulting pairwise comparison matrix is then used to derive normalized weights for each factor.

To ensure the consistency and reliability of expert judgments, a Consistency Ratio (CR) is calculated. A CR value less than or equal to 0.1 indicates that the pairwise comparisons are acceptably consistent. The final Landslide Hazard Index (LHI) is generated through a weighted overlay analysis in a Geographic Information System (GIS), where each factor's raster layer is multiplied by its respective weight and then summed across all layers. The equation to calculate the LHI is provided as follows:

$$\text{LHI} = W_1C_1 + W_2C_2 + W_3C_3 + \dots + W_nC_n \quad (1)$$

where LHI is the Landslide Hazard Index, W_n is the weight of each criterion (derived from AHP), C_n is the normalized value of each criterion (e.g. slope, rainfall, soil type, land use, elevation, etc.), and n is the total number of criteria.

The AHP method requires low to moderate data input, relying primarily on spatial layers of landslide conditioning factors such as slope, geology, rainfall, and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). The AHP method does not require a landslide inventory like the statistical approach, making it especially suitable for data-scarce regions. However, it depends on domain personnel experts and judgment to conduct pairwise comparisons and assign relative importance to each factor. Therefore, the AHP method could be subjective, as it depends heavily on the expert's judgment and lacks statistical validation (Panchal and Shrivastava 2022).

The AHP method is commonly used in preliminary landslide hazard assessments, especially in mountainous or remote areas lacking historical landslide data (Pradhan and Lee 2010). It assumes a linear influence of each factor. It cannot model complex interactions between them, typically resulting in lower predictive accuracy compared to more data-driven or physically based models. Therefore, it is often used as a foundational component in hybrid models integrating statistical methods (Feizizadeh et al. 2013).

Statistical approach

The statistical approach for landslide susceptibility analysis can be broadly classified into two main categories: bivariate and multivariate methods (Mersha and Meten 2020; Shano et al. 2020). The most commonly applied bivariate method is the Frequency Ratio (FR), which evaluates the correlation between landslide occurrences and individual causative factors (Rasyid et al. 2016). In contrast, the most widely used multivariate method is Logistic Regression (LR), which analyzes the combined effect of multiple

Table 1. Pairwise comparison number corresponding to definition.

Value	Definition
1	Equally important
3	Moderately more important
5	Much more important
7	Very much more important
9	Extremely important
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate judgment values

independent variables on landslide susceptibility. The details of each method are discussed in the following sections.

Frequency ratio (FR) method

The Frequency Ratio (FR) method is an effective bivariate statistical approach for landslide hazard mapping. It analyzes the correlation between past landslide occurrences and various conditioning factor classes (e.g. specific slope ranges, lithology types) by calculating the frequency ratio of the area where landslides occurred to the total area for each class. The frequency ratio is the key parameter of the method. It quantifies the likelihood of landslides occurring within a specific attribute class compared to the overall landslide occurrence in the study region. The calculation of the frequency ratio is expressed by Equation 2:

$$FR = \frac{\%L_s}{\%A_m} \quad (2)$$

where FR is the frequency ratio, %L_s is the proportion of landslides in the class, and %A_m is the area of the class as a proportion of the total map. This approach assumes a linear relationship between factors and landslide occurrences, making it simple and computationally efficient. Each class is assigned an FR value, and the final Landslide Hazard Index (LHI), as shown in Equation (3), is generated by summing the FR values across all factor classes.

$$LHI = FR_1 + FR_2 + FR_3 + \dots + FR_n \quad (3)$$

where FR_n is the frequency ratio for each factor class.

The FR method is widely applied for the rapid assessment of landslide-prone zones, particularly in areas where reliable landslide inventories are available. It is commonly used in hazard mapping across diverse geographic settings due to its simplicity and effectiveness. Despite its simplicity, the FR method also has notable limitations. It assumes that all conditioning factors contribute equally to landslide susceptibility, which may not reflect the complexity of real-world interactions (Lee and Pradhan 2007). Additionally, it does not account for multivariate relationships between factors and is less effective in regions with limited or incomplete landslide records. The static nature of the model also makes it unsuitable for dynamic or time-dependent hazard analysis.

Logistic regression (LR) method

The Logistic Regression (LR) method is a widely used multivariate statistical method for landslide hazard mapping, particularly in mountainous regions. It models the probability of landslide occurrence based on the relationship between a binary dependent variable (landslide/no landslide) and multiple independent variables. The logistic function is defined as:

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad \text{where } z = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_nX_n \quad (4)$$

P is the estimated probability of a landslide occurrence, *b*₀ is the intercept, *b*_{*i*} is the slope coefficient of the logistic regression model, and *x*_{*i*} is the independent variable.

The LR method is commonly used for landslide hazard mapping, especially when incorporating both spatial and rainfall-related variables. It also supports temporal analysis, such as using rainfall thresholds in models like the Extreme Rainfall-Induced Landslide Index (IERL) (Vasu et al. 2016). The IERL incorporates parameters such as continuous rainfall, 20-day antecedent rainfall, storage capacity (*S*_{*c*}), and saturated hydraulic conductivity (*K*_{*s*}). These inputs are used to assess how varying rainfall conditions affect landslide probability.

The LR method is effective because it can capture the combined effects of multiple variables, making it more powerful than simple bivariate models. However, it requires a carefully prepared dataset, including balanced sampling, proper variable selection, and normalization. The model assumes a linear relationship

between the independent variables and the log-odds of landslide occurrence, which may oversimplify complex natural systems (Brenning 2005).

Semi-quantitative and statistical hybrid approach

A Semi-Quantitative and Statistical Hybrid Approach in landslide hazard mapping combines the expert-based nature of semi-quantitative methods (like the Analytic Hierarchy Process, AHP) with the data-driven objectivity of statistical models (like Frequency Ratio, FR, Logistic Regression, LR, or Fuzzy Logistic, FL). This hybridization leverages the strengths of both approaches while minimizing their individual limitations. This hybrid method enhances the accuracy of the landslide hazard mapping where limited landslide data exist, but expert knowledge is available. It is especially useful in comparative studies for benchmarking different approaches, and in applications where hybrid solutions are needed to balance data scarcity and modeling rigor. For example, Feizizadeh et al. (2013) and Abdi et al. (2021) both combined the AHP and FL methods to evaluate the landslide hazard mapping and concluded that the hybrid AHP + FL method provides a higher accuracy in the landslide mapping. The Hybrid AHP + FR + LR model with penalty weighting is developed to integrate expert judgment, bivariate statistical evidence, and multivariate regression for landslide hazard mapping. Converting FR to Weight of Evidence using logarithm function is selected due to its simplicity, transparency, and compatibility with the LR framework. Furthermore, the FR method is commonly employed by the Department of Mineral Resources (DMR) in Thailand to create landslide susceptibility maps (DMR 2022). To account for the relative importance of conditioning factors, the penalty-weighted logistic regression is introduced into the hybrid model. The inclusion of the penalized LR not only reduces multicollinearity and overfitting issues inherent in conventional regression but also allows stronger predictors to exert greater influence while constraining weaker variables. This combination improves predictive accuracy, as discussed in the following sections. The non-continuous conditioning factors such as geology are first quantified using their respective Frequency Ratio (FR) values, providing a numerical measure of the statistical association between each category and landslide occurrence. Then they are converted to WOE (Equation 5), combined with continuous variables in their original form, and are then used as inputs to a ridge-regularized or penalty-weighted logistic regression (LR) model (Hoerl and Kennard 1970) in which variable-specific penalty factors are derived from the AHP weights. In this penalty-weighted framework, factors assigned higher importance through AHP receive smaller penalties, allowing them to exert greater influence in the model, while less important factors are penalized more heavily.

$$\text{WOE} = \ln (FR) \quad (5)$$

The AHP weights are converted into penalty factors (\varnothing_j) for the penalized LR using:

$$\varnothing_j = \frac{1}{w_j + \varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

where w_j is the AHP weight and ε is a small positive constant to avoid division by zero. Then the factor penalty (λ_j) was calculate using Equation 7.

$$\lambda_j = \lambda_{base} \times \varnothing_j \quad (7)$$

where λ_j is the global regularization strength, which applied to all predictors before adjusting for their AHP-derived importance. In this study, the penalized logistic regression loss function was computed using Equation (8), which incorporates variable-specific penalties derived from the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) weights.

$$L(\beta) = - \sum_{i=1}^n [\log p_i + (1 - y_i) \log (1 - p_i)] + \sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j \beta^2 \quad (8)$$

where $L(\beta)$ is a penalized loss function, n is the number of observations (pixels, samples), p is the number of predictors (conditioning factors), $y_i \in \{0,1\}$ is the observed landslide occurrence at sample i , p_i is the predicted probability of landslide at sample i , β_j = coefficient of predictor j . To ensure comparability across predictors with different measurement scales, all input factors were standardized prior to model fitting. Each variable x_j was transformed into a standardized form $x_j^* = (x_j - \mu_j)/\sigma_j$, where μ_j and σ_j represent the mean and standard deviation of the factor, respectively. This standardization allowed the regression coefficients to be estimated on a consistent scale, improving model stability and interpretability under penalization. The optimized loss function was then minimized to obtain the final coefficients, and the logistic regression equation was established. Using this fitted LR equation, the Landslide Hazard Index (LHI) was subsequently calculated to generate the susceptibility map.

This Hybrid AHP + FR + LR model with penalty weighting allows the LR stage to simultaneously incorporate empirical evidence from FR and expert-assigned importance from AHP, enabling the model to capture multivariate interactions and nonlinear effects while maintaining the transparency of FR quantification for categorical variables. The resulting hybrid AHP–FR–penalized LR methodology integrates statistical, expert-based, and multivariate modeling strengths to achieve improved landslide hazard mapping accuracy compared to traditional FR or AHP–FR approaches.

Deterministic approach

The deterministic approach uses the geotechnical engineering theory to analyze slope stability through the mechanical properties of soil and rock. This approach is particularly effective for small-scale mapping, offering precise information for evaluating mass movement. Research on slope failures has utilized geotechnical-based models such as SINMAP, TRIGRS, SHALSTAB, and others (Vieira et al. 2018; Manan et al. 2022). Each model has its own strengths and limitations. Landslide hazard mapping has recently been applied in various regions using geotechnical or physically based approaches.

One of the most successfully applied models for landslide hazard mapping using the deterministic approach is the Transient Rainfall Infiltration and Grid-based Regional Slope-Stability Analysis (TRIGRS). TRIGRS is widely used for high-resolution, site-specific hazard assessments, particularly in areas requiring detailed simulation of slope responses to rainfall events. It is well-suited for real-time or forecast-based early warning systems, as well as for modeling rainfall thresholds and the temporal progression of landslide initiation (Baum et al. 2008; Ciurleo et al. 2019). It employs a time-dependent approach to develop a deterministic model that simulates shallow ground stability under increasing rainfall, accounting for transient pressure changes and downward infiltration processes. Based on the linearized solution from Iverson (2000), TRIGRS accounts for transient changes in pore water pressure caused by rainfall infiltration and models slope stability using the infinite slope method.

TRIGRS calculates the total infiltrated water (I_z) as the sum of precipitation (P) and upstream runoff (RU), constrained by the saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s) of the soil. When infiltration exceeds this limit, excess water generates downstream runoff (RD). These hydrologic dynamics are governed by equations that relate rainfall intensity and soil permeability to infiltration and runoff behavior, as shown in Equation (9).

$$I_z = K_s \text{ or } P + \text{RU} > K_s \text{ and } \text{RD} = P + \text{RU} - K_s \quad (9)$$

This formulation allows TRIGRS to account for the dynamic interactions between rainfall intensity, soil permeability, and surface water movement, thereby enhancing the accuracy of rainfall-induced landslide prediction. TRIGRS utilizes the equation, as shown in Equation (10), proposed by Iverson (2000) to estimate the pressure head response (φ) over time and depth under varying rainfall conditions. This function allows the model to simulate how rainfall affects slope stability across a landscape. The hydraulic diffusivity presented in Equation (9) further characterizes the capacity of the soil to transmit water.

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(Z, t) = [Z - d]\beta + 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{I_{nz}}{K_z} H(t - t_n) [D_1(t - t_n)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \text{ierfc} \left[\frac{(2m-1)d_{LZ} - (d_{LZ} - Z)}{2[D_1(t - t_n)]^{1/2}} \right] \\ & + \text{ierfc} \left[\frac{(2m-1)d_{LZ} - (d_{LZ} - Z)}{2[D_1(t - t_n)]^{1/2}} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \\ - 2 \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{I_{nz}}{K_z} H(t - t_{n+1}) [D_1(t - t_{n+1})]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \text{ierfc} \left[\frac{(2m-1)d_{LZ} - (d_{LZ} - Z)}{2[D_1(t - t_{n+1})]^{1/2}} \right] \\ & + \text{ierfc} \left[\frac{(2m-1)d_{LZ} - (d_{LZ} - Z)}{2[D_1(t - t_{n+1})]^{1/2}} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\varphi(Z, t)$ denotes the groundwater pressure head at variable time, t , and variable depth, Z , in the vertical direction. $Z = \frac{z}{\cos \theta}$ (where z is a variable in normal slope direction, it means the depth of failure on the inclined plane). $\beta = \lambda \cos \theta$ where $\lambda = \cos \theta - \left(\frac{I_{nz}}{K_z} \right)_{LT}$, in which K_z is the hydraulic conductivity in the Z direction. I_z is the steady surface flux, and I_{nz} is the surface flux, which got the intensity of the n^{th} time-interval, where n is the total number of timings. D_0 is the hydraulic diffusivity. $H(t-t_n)$ is the heavy side function, where $D_1 = D_0/\cos^2 \theta$, and the error function, $\text{ierfc}(\eta)$, is shown below:

$$\text{ierfc}(\eta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \exp(-\eta)^2 - \mu \text{erfc}(\eta) \quad (11)$$

where $\text{ierfc}(\eta)$ is the error function. The hydraulic diffusivity (D_0) is presented in Equation 12.

$$D_0 = \frac{K_s}{S_s} \quad (12)$$

where K_s is the hydraulic conductivity and S_s is the specific storage.

Slope stability analysis in TRIGRS uses the infinite slope method to calculate the Factor of Safety (FS) based on the Coulomb failure criterion. The stability equation used in TRIGRS is presented as follows:

$$\text{Factor of Safety (FS)} = \frac{\tan \varnothing'}{\tan \theta} + \frac{C' - \gamma_w \varphi(Z, t) \tan \varnothing'}{\gamma_w Z \sin \theta \cos \theta} \quad (13)$$

where c is the soil cohesion, \varnothing is the soil friction angle, φ is the groundwater pressure head as a function of depth (Z) and time (t). θ is the slope angle. γ_w and γ_s are water and soil unit weights, respectively.

TRIGRS offers a physically based representation of the processes governing rainfall-induced slope failure. It produces time-evolving hazard maps and is highly accurate when calibrated using field and laboratory data. However, based on the authors' experience, the method is data and resource-intensive, making it less practical for large regions or data-scarce environments. It also requires significant computational resources, with time-consuming preprocessing and calibration steps. Furthermore, this method is not suitable for modeling deep-seated or wedge-type landslides.

Study site information

The Ardi Watershed study site is located in the Mae Yao sub-district of the Mueang district in Chiang Rai province, northern Thailand. Figure 1 shows the location of the study site. As shown in Figure 1, the area of the study site is characterized by a mountainous landscape with a plateau nestled between the mountains. The topography follows a north-south orientation, with elevations ranging from 400 to 1,200 meters above sea level. The area of Ardi Watershed is predominantly mountainous and forested, while the middle part is primarily utilized for agriculture. The typical temperature in the Ardi Watershed ranges between 19.5 and 27.5 °C. The rainy season spans from May to September, while the summer occurs from February to April, with an average annual rainfall of 1,500 mm and a relative humidity of 77.83%. Winter months last from October through January (DMR 2011).

Figure 1. Location of the Ardi Watershed study site.

Geological features

The geological map of the Ardi Watershed study site is presented in [Figure 2](#). [Figure 2](#) shows a variety of rock formations. In the middle part, Silurian–Devonian (SD) rocks consist of low-grade metamorphic rocks such as phyllite, schist, and quartzite. Devonian–Carboniferous (DC) rocks, are located in the western part, including dark-colored quartzite, shale, limestone, pyroclastic rock, and chert. The Carboniferous–Permian (CP) group contains gray sandstone interbedded with gray shale, siltstone with volcanic rock clasts, and reddish conglomerate. The Triassic Plutonic rocks, primarily granite, occur throughout the region, classified as Trgr2 (biotite and hornblende–biotite granite) and Trgr1 (biotite granite with large phenocrysts). Additional rock types include diorite and hornblendite, both found in the western zone. The Ardi Watershed is also covered by Quaternary sediments, including terrace deposits (gravel, sand, silt, and laterite), alluvium (clayey sand interbedded with sand, gravel, and lateritic soil), and floodplain clay. (DMR 2011).

Landslide and debris flow event

On September 8, 2020, the Ardi Watershed study area experienced a flash flood and debris flow event triggered by intense rainfall, which damaged approximately 20 houses. [Figure 3](#) presents examples of the damage caused by this event. Rainfall data from nearby weather stations were analyzed and are shown in [Figure 4](#). According to the data, rainfall began around 00:00 AM, intensifying by 5:00 AM and peaking at 65 mm. By that time, the cumulative hourly rainfall had reached 210 mm. The extreme precipitation saturated the mountainside, initiating landslides that evolved into debris flows. By 6:00 AM, these debris flows had descended the slopes and reached Ardi Village, causing significant damage and disruption.

This event highlights the high susceptibility of the Ardi Watershed study area to rainfall-induced landslides, emphasizing the need for hazard assessment and mitigation strategies in the region. A review of

Figure 2. Geological map of the Ardi Watershed.

historical meteorological data and local reports indicates that while the region experiences seasonal monsoons, no significant rainfall-triggered disasters of comparable magnitude have been documented prior to 2020 (DMR 2022). Therefore, there is also a limitation of the evidence of the landslide scar for this reason.

Field investigations

Understanding the geological and geophysical conditions of the Ardi Watershed study site is essential for evaluating landslide hazards in the region. This section presents the results of detailed geological mapping and geophysical investigations, which were carried out to refine lithological boundaries, identify structural features, and assess geomorphological evidence of fault activity. These findings, combined with landslide inventory mapping and geophysical surveys, provide critical insight for the landslide hazard mapping analyzes described in the following sections.

Geological investigation

Field investigations in the Ardi Watershed study area resulted in updates to previously mapped geological boundaries and included direct measurements of structural features to assess geomechanical conditions. The primary joint structures were recorded to be oriented at the following dip angles and strikes: $60^{\circ}/275^{\circ}$, $79^{\circ}/348^{\circ}$, $32^{\circ}/148^{\circ}$, and $75^{\circ}/037^{\circ}$, respectively.

The geological investigation revealed that highly fractured rock outcrops are prominent along the creek, indicating a history of structural instability and potential susceptibility to mass movement. The Department of Mineral Resources, Thailand, reports that the Ardi Watershed is within the Mae Chan Fault Zone, an active fault system (DMR 2011). Our field observations confirmed the presence of

Figure 3. Damage caused by the September 8, 2020, flash flood and debris flow event.

triangular facets, which serve as geomorphological indicators of active fault movement. Moreover, satellite imagery analysis highlights the presence of a fault lineament passing through the watershed, with drainage patterns aligning with the fault trace, which further supports evidence of tectonic activity in the region.

The landslide scars in the study area were identified using aerial photographs from the Geotechnical Engineering Research and Development Center (GERD) (GERD 2022) and confirmed through our field observations. The landslide inventory map containing the observed landslide scars is shown in Figure 5. Figure 6 shows examples of the landslide scars observed in the study area. Most scars were classified as shallow landslides based on the classification by Deere and Patton (1971). The landslide scars are typically found on steep slopes near creeks, with widths of 20 to 100 m and depths of 1 to 3 m. The scars are generally located at the interface between residual soil and bedrock (Completely weathered layer, CW). The concentration of shallow landslides in fractured zones underscores the influence of structural geology, slope angle, and hydrology on rainfall-induced slope failure. These observations highlight the need for detailed hazard assessment and mitigation in the area.

Figure 4. Record of hourly rainfall and cumulative hourly rainfall on September 8, 2020.

Figure 5. Landslide inventory map with landslide scars observed in the study area.

Geophysical investigation

Geophysical investigations in the Ardi Watershed aimed to assess subsurface conditions and support slope stability analysis. Two methods were used: electrical imaging (EI) to map subsurface resistivity, and seismic

Figure 6. Examples of the landslide scars observed in the study area.

refraction to measure P -wave velocity for interpreting subsurface layering. The area is predominantly granite, with shale and mudstone also present. Differentiating between residual soil and completely weathered (CW) rock using resistivity alone is challenging due to overlapping values. Therefore, seismic refraction, which provides distinct P -wave velocities, was used to improve soil thickness estimation and subsurface modeling accuracy.

Electrical imaging was performed with 1 m electrode spacing using a Wenner array with 48 electrodes, while seismic refraction used 1 m geophone spacing and 24 geophones. Figure 7a presents a cut slope for granitic weathering material used for calibration of geophysical results. The results of the electric imaging are shown in Figure 7b, presenting the CW rock ranges from 300 to 1500 Ωm , while the residual soil ranges from 1500 to 12000 Ωm . The seismic refraction result (Figure 7c) indicates velocity values of 1039 m/s for the CW rock and 295 m/s for the residual soil.

The geophysical survey results for the Carboniferous–Permian (CP) rock are shown in Figure 8. Figures 8a and 8b present electrical imaging results ranging from 300 to 9000 Ωm for the CW layer and 500 to 9000 Ωm for the residual soil layer. The seismic refraction result (Figure 8c) indicates velocities of 442 m/s for the CW rock and 295 m/s for the residual soil. Due to overlapping properties, neither method alone could clearly distinguish the layers. However, integrating EI and seismic refraction data provides a more accurate distinction between subsurface materials. The soil thickness for both Granite and CP soils ranges from 1 to 10 m, depending on the slope angle, with steeper slopes having lower thicknesses compared to flatter slopes.

Laboratory testing

As mentioned above, the watershed is covered by Granite, Sedimentary rocks grouped in Carboniferous–Permian (CP), and Silurian–Devonian (SD) rocks with low-grade metamorphic rocks. However, due to difficult terrain and accessibility limitations, only the disturbed and undisturbed samples of Granite and CP units were collected. Consequently, typical values determined from a review of relevant literature were used in the analyzes.

The laboratory testing, including grain size distribution, hydrometer tests, Atterberg limits, hydraulic conductivity tests, and direct shear tests, was conducted in the geotechnical engineering laboratory at the

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 7. Geophysical investigation results for granitic unit: (a) actual cut slope section, (b) electric imaging result, and (c) seismic refraction result.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. Geophysical investigation results for carboniferous–perman (cp) unit: (a) electric imaging result of location 1 with 14-degree slope, (b) electric imaging result of location 2 with 30-degree slope, and (c) seismic refraction result of location 2.

Asian Institute of Technology. The results of the laboratory tests were summarized in [Table 2](#) and were used in our landslide hazard mapping analyzes.

Landslide hazard mapping analyzes

This section presents a comparative analysis of landslide hazard mapping techniques applied to the Ardi Watershed study area. Four landslide hazard mapping approaches, including the semi-quantitative (AHP) approach, the statistical (FR and LR) approach, the semi-quantitative and statistical hybrid (AHP + FR + Penalty LR) approach, and the deterministic (TRIGRS) approach, were used to generate landslide hazard maps. Each approach incorporates a unique modeling framework, using combinations of spatial, geotechnical, and rainfall data. The digital elevation model and other spatial maps with a 5-meter resolution were utilized. Compared to the landslide inventory (width of 20 to 100 m), this resolution can accurately capture the scar area. The landslide inventory map shown in [Figure 5](#) was used for model validation. To assess the predictive performance of each mapping approach and classification method, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) from the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis was applied (Fawcett 2006). Moreover, other statistical values, including TPR, FPR, precision, and F1 were calculated. [Table 3](#) presents the performance of the model according to the AUC value (Abul Hasanat et al. 2010). This allowed for the quantitative evaluation of how well each model identified known landslide locations.

Rainfall intensity is a key temporal triggering factor in landslide occurrences (Morya et al. 2019; Amarathunga et al. 2022). When conducting the landslide hazard mapping analyzes, rainfall intensity must be classified into discrete intervals to apply to the landslide hazard modeling. Therefore, selecting an appropriate rainfall classification method is essential to enhance model performance and prediction accuracy. Different rainfall intensity classification methods, including the 10 mm, 40 mm, K-means method, and Logistic Regression (LR) models, were evaluated in this study to determine the appropriate rainfall intensity for landslide hazard mapping. Fixed-interval classifications (10 mm and 40 mm) and K-Means clustering divide rainfall into discrete groups, but these approaches create artificial thresholds that may lead to misclassification of hazard zones, as they do not fully capture the continuous nature of rainfall variation. In contrast, the LR method predicts rainfall intensity as a continuous value and directly establishes a statistical relationship between rainfall intensity and landslide occurrences, eliminating the issue of artificial boundaries. The LR model in this study incorporated both hourly and three-day cumulative rainfall data, but the cumulative term was excluded due to the absence of preceding rainfall during the September 8, 2020 event. The Z equation in [Equation \(4\)](#) is expressed as:

$$Z = -5.296950 + (0.067358 \times \text{Daily Rainfall}) + (b \times 3 - \text{Day Rainfall Accumulation}) \quad (14)$$

Table 2. Summary of laboratory test results.

Soil property	Granite	CP
Cohesion (kPa)	15.69	17.94
Friction angle (Degree)	27	19.16
Dry unit weight (N/m ³)	12.58	13.84
Hydraulic conductivity (m/s)	9.78×10^{-7}	2.31×10^{-5}
Liquid limit (%)	42.79	38.72
Plastic limit (%)	31.88	20.87
USCS classification	SM	SC

Table 3. Performance of the area under curve (AUC) values.

AUC	Performance
0.90–1.00	Excellent
0.80–0.90	Good
0.70–0.80	Fair
0.60–0.70	Poor
0.50–0.60	Very poor

where Z represents the log-odds of landslide occurrence. The model achieved a McFadden's R^2 value of 0.321, indicating a relatively good fit. Different rainfall models were tested using the FR mapping model, and performance comparisons confirmed that the LR approach produced the highest AUC score of 68.48%, outperforming the 10 mm, 40 mm, and K-Means classifications (62.18%, 61.14%, and 66.24%, respectively). This demonstrates that the LR-based classification provides the most accurate and reliable landslide hazard mapping, offering pixel-based continuous probability values rather than interval-based groupings. As such, the LR method was chosen for the rainfall classification in this study. This study also evaluated the performance of various zonation techniques by classifying the landslide hazard index (LHI) into five categories: very low, low, moderate, high, and very high. The three zonation methods used were Geometrical Interval (GI), Quantile (QT), and Natural Break (NB). Assuming that high and very high hazard zones correspond to actual landslide occurrences, the area under the curve (AUC) was assessed. However, since geotechnical engineering or deterministic approaches model landslides using the factor of safety (FS), areas with an FS less than 1 were considered landslide-prone in the AUC evaluation. In deterministic models, $FS < 1$ is universally adopted as the threshold for landslide initiation, as it directly represents the physical condition under which slope instability develops. Using $FS < 1$ to define landslide areas in the AUC evaluation ensures consistency between geotechnical theory and hazard mapping, allowing the results to reflect actual slope failure mechanisms.

The following sections describe the results for the methods used to generate landslide hazard maps, the rainfall intensity data applied, and the AUC-based validation results across different model classification strategies.

Analyzes using semi-quantitative approach

As mentioned in the previous section, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method is one of the widely used semi-quantitative methods that applies systematic decision-making to landslide mapping. Therefore, details of the landslide hazard mapping using the AHP method are provided in this section.

Eight factors, including daily rainfall, geology, slope, elevation, aspect, distance to drainage, distance to lineament, and NDVI, were selected for the pairwise comparison analysis and are shown in Table 4. These factors were chosen based on the literature review, site-specific characteristics, previous studies, and our experience (DMR 2022). To ensure the reliability of the statistical analysis, multicollinearity among the conditioning factors was examined using both pairwise correlation coefficients (Pearson and Spearman) and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The correlation analysis revealed no pairs of variables with excessively high correlation coefficients ($|r| > 0.8$), indicating that the factors are not strongly linearly dependent. Furthermore, the VIF results for all variables were consistently below 2, far lower than the commonly accepted thresholds of 5 (moderate) or 10 (severe) for multicollinearity concerns (Putriani et al. 2023). This demonstrates that the explanatory variables are statistically independent, allowing them to be retained in the subsequent analyzes without risk of bias from redundancy.

Based on landslide evidence and previous studies, geology, and slope are the most influential factors in landslide susceptibility assessment (Pradhan and Lee 2010; Myronidis et al. 2016). Moreover, rainfall is recognized as the primary triggering factor, making it the most critical parameter for this study. A pairwise

Table 4. Pairwise comparison results for the AHP approach.

Factor No.	Item description	Slope (degree)	NDVI	Geology	Elevation (m)	Distance to lineament (m)	Distance to drainage (m)	Aspect	Rainfall (mm/day)	Weight
1	Slope (degree)	1.0	6.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	3.0	5.0	0.5	0.210
2	NDVI	0.2	1.0	0.2	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	0.2	0.045
3	Geology	1.0	6.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	3.0	5.0	0.5	0.210
4	Elevation (m)	0.3	1.0	0.3	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	0.2	0.066
5	Distance to lineament (m)	0.3	2.0	0.3	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.2	0.055
6	Distance to drainage (m)	0.3	1.0	0.3	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	0.3	0.065
7	Aspect	0.2	1.0	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.2	0.042
8	Rainfall (mm/day)	2.0	6.0	2.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	6.0	1.0	0.307

comparison matrix using Saaty's scale to express the relative importance of one factor over another was constructed. The pairwise comparison matrix was adjusted based on expert judgment and validated through sensitivity analysis to ensure accurate weighting of landslide conditioning factors. A consistency check was performed to validate the expert judgments. This involved calculating the Consistency Index (CI) and the Consistency Ratio (CR), which compare the logical consistency of the matrix to a randomly generated matrix. The CR value was calculated as 0.02 for the weights in Table 4. The final weight assignments are presented in Table 4.

The final Landslide Hazard Index (LHI) for each pixel was computed using the weights shown in Table 4 by a weighted overlay technique in GIS. The resulting LHI values were then classified into susceptibility zones (very low, low, moderate, high, and very high). Figure 9 presents the resulting landslide hazard mapping using the AHP approach for the study site.

The AHP-based landslide hazard map shown in Figure 9 was validated using the landslide inventory map in Figure 5. The Quantile (QT) method provided the best validation values. The AUC, TPR, FPR, precision, and F1 for the AHP-generated landslide hazard map were 68.03%, 31%, 16%, 44%, and 36%, respectively. This result indicates a poor to moderate predictive capability, highlighting the suitability but also the need for improvement in the AHP-based landslide hazard assessment for the Ardi Watershed study site.

Analyzes using statistical approach

As discussed earlier, the Frequency Ratio (FR) method is the most commonly used bivariate method in the statistical approach. On the other hand, the Logistic Regression (LR) method is the most widely applied multivariate method in the statistical approach. Details of the landslide hazard mapping using the FR and LR methods are provided in the following sections.

Figure 9. Landslide hazard mapping using the AHP approach.

Frequency ratio (FR) method

In this section, the Frequency Ratio (FR) method was used to quantify the relationship between historical landslide occurrences and conditioning factors that contribute to slope instability. The landslide inventory map shown in Figure 5 and the relevant conditioning factors shown in Table 4 were used in the statistical analysis. Each factor was reclassified into categorical classes to facilitate statistical analysis. For each class within a conditioning factor, the FR value was calculated. For the rainfall conditioning factor, the value from the LR model was used as the input value for each pixel location in the FR-based landslide hazard mapping process. The highest calculated FR values for the conditioning factors were summarized in Table 5. All of the FR values shown in Table 5 are greater than 1, indicating a higher susceptibility to landslides.

After calculating the FR values for all classes, each raster layer representing a conditioning factor was interval classified, so that each cell was assigned the FR weight based on its class. These FR-weighted rasters were then summed using a raster calculator in GIS, resulting in a Landslide Hazard Index (LHI) for each cell. The final LHI map was then classified into landslide hazard zones. Figure 10 presents the resulting landslide hazard mapping using the FR approach for the study site.

The resulting landslide hazard map using the FR approach was validated using the AUC metric. The AUC value for the landslide hazard map generated using the FR approach was 68.48%, zoning with the Natural Breaks (NB) method. The TPR, FPR, precision, and F1 were 29%, 15%, 41%, and 34%, respectively. The FR model demonstrated a poor to moderate predictive capability, indicating its capability but also highlighting the need for improvement in identifying landslide-hazard areas.

Logistic regression (LR) method

The Logistic Regression (LR) method was used to model the probability of landslide occurrence based on the relationship between a binary dependent variable (landslide presence or absence) and multiple independent variables (conditioning factors). The landslide inventory map shown in Figure 5 and the relevant conditioning factors shown in Table 4 were used in the statistical analysis. Each landslide and non-landslide location was assigned values 1 and 0, respectively, forming the basis of the input dataset for the logistic regression analysis. To develop a statistically robust landslide hazard model, 20,000 data points were randomly selected from the dataset. To ensure a balanced representation between landslide (failure) and non-landslide (non-failure) areas, a 1:1 ratio was used for data selection, as recommended by Woodard and Mirus (2023). This balanced dataset enhances model stability and prediction accuracy. The McFadden's R^2 value for the LR model was calculated as 0.215, indicating a good model fit and suggesting that the selected landslide conditioning factors contribute significantly to landslide susceptibility prediction (McFadden 1977; Clark and Hosking 1986). The LR equation shown in Equation (4) was developed to estimate the probability of landslide occurrence, P . The Z equation in Equation (4) was determined and is shown in Equation (15).

$$Z = -5.05492 + (0.06417 \times \text{rainfall}) + (-0.00033 \times \text{aspect}) + (-1.50676 \times \text{ndvi}) + (-0.00062 \\ \times \text{distance to lineament}) + (-0.00331 \times \text{distance to drainage}) + (-0.00239 \times \text{elevation}) \\ + (0.03797 \times \text{slope}) + \text{geology} \quad (15)$$

Table 5. The most susceptible class for each factor from the FR values.

Factor	Most susceptible class	FR value
Slope angle (Degree)	50–60	3.00
NDVI	0.08–0.20	1.70
Geology	Silurian–Devonian (SD)	2.38
Elevation (m)	600–700	1.58
Distance to lineament (m)	0–200	1.26
Distance to drainage (m)	50–100	1.18
Aspect	North-facing slopes	1.35

Figure 10. Landslide hazard mapping using the FR approach.

The regression coefficients shown in Equation (15) were derived using a maximum likelihood estimation approach, determining the best-fitting model that relates the predictor variables to the landslide occurrence. Once the model was calibrated, the logistic equation was applied to each pixel in the study area by substituting raster values for each factor, resulting in a landslide probability map where each pixel is assigned a value between 0 (least likely to fail) and 1 (most likely to fail). The resulting probability map was then classified into hazard zones. The resulting landslide hazard mapping using the LR approach for the study site is presented in Figure 11.

The AUC value for the landslide hazard map was calculated to evaluate the model's predictive performance. The AUC, TPR, FPR, precision, and F1 using the LR and classified by the GI zonation method, were 70.57%, 29%, 14%, 45%, and 36%, respectively. It demonstrates poor to moderate mapping capability. The strength of the LR approach lies in its ability to establish direct relationships between landslide occurrence and causative factors, making it more objective than the AHP approach and less dependent on the size of the landslide inventory than the FR approach. However, the LR approach requires a well-balanced dataset, which was achieved in this study through random sampling of 20,000 data points with a 1:1 failure to non-failure ratio.

Analyzes using semi-quantitative and statistical hybrid approach

As mentioned in the previous sections, the hybrid approach that combines semi-quantitative and statistical methods improves the accuracy of the landslide hazard mapping, particularly in areas where landslide inventory data are limited but expert knowledge is available. The hybrid AHP-FR-Penalty Weighted Logistic Regression model successfully integrated expert knowledge, categorical quantification, and multivariate statistical learning for landslide hazard mapping. Geology (non-continuous variable) was first quantified using Frequency Ratio (FR), providing an objective, data-driven measure of their association with landslides. Then they are transformed into WOE. These WOE values together with continuous

Figure 11. Landslide hazard mapping using the LR approach.

factors, were then entered into a ridge-regularized logistic regression (LR) model. AHP-derived weights were used to define variable-specific penalty factors ??, such that highly important factors (e.g. geology, rainfall, slope) were penalized less, while less influential factors (e.g. aspect, NDVI) were penalized more. This formulation allowed the regression to preserve expert-driven priorities while still capturing multivariate interactions.

The relevant conditioning factors shown in Table 4 were used in the statistical analysis. The landslide inventory map shown in Figure 5 was used to calculate frequency ratios. The estimated logit function is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z = & -0.1671 + (0.8460 \times \text{rainfall}^*) + (0.0272 \times \text{aspect}^*) + (-0.1274 \times \text{ndvi}^*) \\
 & + (-0.1366 \times \text{distance to lineament}^*) + (-0.3003 \times \text{distance to drainage}^*) \\
 & + (-0.1207 \times \text{elevation}^*) + (0.2437 \times \text{slope}^*) + (0.9587 \times \text{WOE of geology}^*)
 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

This equation highlights rainfall, geology, and slope as the most influential predictors, consistent with prior knowledge of rainfall-induced landslides. Weaker contributions from NDVI and aspect align with their lower AHP weights and FR values. The resulting LHI raster was then classified into hazard categories. The resulting landslide hazard mapping using the hybrid AHP-FR-Penalty Weighted Logistic Regression for the study site is presented in Figure 12.

In terms of model performance, the penalty-weighted LR achieved a McFadden R^2 of 0.232 (Traditional LR is 0.215), indicating good discriminatory power and calibration. The AUC analysis was performed to assess this hybrid model's predictive capability. The AUC, TPR, FPR, precision, and F1 using the penalty-weighted LR, classified by the NB zonation method, were 81.53%, 67%, 29%, 23%, and 34%, respectively. It demonstrates moderate to good mapping capability. Compared to the AUC values of 68.48% 68.03%, and 70.57% obtained for the FR, AHP, LR methods, respectively, this approach improves predictive accuracy by explicitly handling multicollinearity, penalizing weak predictors, and capturing interactions among conditioning factors. Overall, this hybrid strategy demonstrates that combining FR (for

Figure 12. Landslide hazard mapping using the hybrid AHP–FR–penalty weighted logistic regression approach.

categorical quantification), AHP (for penalty weighting), and penalized LR (for robust multivariate modeling) provides a more interpretable and statistically powerful framework for landslide hazard mapping.

Analyzes using deterministic approach

One of the most common models for landslide hazard mapping using the deterministic approach is the Transient Rainfall Infiltration and Grid-based Regional Slope–Stability Analysis (TRIGRS) method. Therefore, the TRIGRS method was utilized in this study to generate the landslide hazard map and compare it to other approaches used in this study.

The TRIGRS model requires the following inputs: a high-resolution DEM, hourly rainfall data, initial groundwater depths, and detailed geotechnical properties. In Thailand, it is common to generalize soil parameters by geological unit for spatial geotechnical modeling (Torvivat 2009). Accordingly, the parameters for the TRIGRS model were primarily obtained from the laboratory tests and calibrated sources. The properties for the granitic and Carboniferous–Permian (CP) units were selected from lab testing, including adjustments for granitic residual soil from Parapan et al. (2024), while values for the Silurian–Devonian (SD) and Devonian–Carboniferous (DC) units were adopted from Torvivat (2009), who tested over 500 soil samples across Thailand. The soil parameters used in this study are summarized in Table 6.

In addition to soil properties, soil thickness, a critical input for infiltration modeling, was estimated using geophysical investigations in the Ardi Watershed area. The electrical resistivity and seismic *P*-wave velocity data indicated that the soil thickness across the area ranges from 1 to 10 meters. A spatial soil depth distribution was generated using a linear relationship between elevation and thickness, as well as slope and thickness, following the method of Saulnier et al. (1997), to account for topographic variability. When comparing the two models, the soil thickness related topography presented a higher AUC, and

Table 6. Summary of parameters used in the TRIGRS model.

Soil property	Granite	CP	SD	DC
Cohesion (N/m ²)	15,691	10,000	12,000	19,000
Friction angle (Degrees)	27	28.52	30.14	22.91
Unit weight (N/m ³)	18,437	17,400	16,400	16,500
Permeability (m/s)	9.78×10^{-7}	2.31×10^{-5}	1.73×10^{-5}	2.05×10^{-5}
Residual vol. water content	0.098	0.011	0.013	0.016
Saturated vol. water content	0.42	0.41	0.43	0.42
Alpha parameter (1/m)	0.170	0.048	0.115	0.048
Hydraulic diffusivity (m ² /s)	1.47×10^{-4}	3.47×10^{-3}	2.60×10^{-3}	3.08×10^{-3}
Steady infiltration rate (m/s)	9.78×10^{-9}	2.31×10^{-7}	1.73×10^{-7}	2.05×10^{-7}

Figure 13. Hourly rainfall distribution map generated by the IDW method with a power of 1.

consistent with the field data. Therefore, it was chosen for the analysis. This enhanced the realism of the input depth layers for the TRIGRS model.

Another key input for the TRIGRS model is the initial groundwater level, which directly affects the generation of pore water pressure during rainfall events. In this study, the bedrock depth was approximately 10 meters, and groundwater levels were varied around this depth based on the nearby groundwater well data (DGR, 2022) to assess their influence on slope stability.

Rainfall, particularly the intense storm on September 8, 2020, is identified as the primary triggering factor in this landslide analysis. Modeling rainfall data, especially in unsaturated soils, could be challenging (Chao et al. 2014). Hourly rainfall data from seven meteorological stations were interpolated using the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) method to create spatially distributed rainfall maps. Different power functions ranging from 1 to 5 were tested to optimize the accuracy of the interpolation, and validation against two independent stations (refer to Figure 4) showed that a power of 1 resulted in the lowest Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value of 0.218. The hourly rainfall distribution map generated by the IDW method with a power of 1 is shown in Figure 13. Consequently, the IDW interpolation with a power of 1 was used to generate the hourly rainfall inputs for the TRIGRS model.

The TRIGRS simulation was run using the hourly rainfall data, soil thickness, and geotechnical parameters to model pore pressure evolution and rainfall-induced slope failure over 24 hours. The model's parameter calibration and sensitivity were evaluated by varying the strength parameters and permeability from their average values, as reported by Torvivat (2009), and through laboratory testing. Then parameters from the maximum AUC model were chosen for mapping.

The resulting FS maps show the dynamic progression of instability, and the FS map at the 24-hour mark was used for validation, as it corresponds to the timing of the landslide inventory mapping activity. The factor of safety (FS) map, representing landslide hazard, was classified into two categories: stable areas ($FS \geq 1$) and failure or landslide areas ($FS < 1$). The factor of safety (FS) map was subsequently compared with the landslide inventory to assess the accuracy of the approach. Figure 14 illustrates the landslide hazard mapping using the TRIGRS method, with an initial groundwater level set at 10 meters.

The AUC, TPR, FPR, precision, and F1 for the landslide hazard map using the TRIGRS model were 88.97%, 61%, 11%, 67%, 64%, respectively. This AUC value indicates the TRIGRS model's good performance in landslide hazard mapping, demonstrating its effectiveness in capturing landslide-prone zones, particularly when accurately representing soil, rainfall, and groundwater conditions.

Comparison of landslide hazard mapping techniques

This section presents a comparative evaluation of five different approaches (AHP, FR, LR, AHP + FR + Penalty LR, and TRIGRS) used in the study to assess the landslide hazard in the Ardi Watershed study area. The comparison focuses on their methodological and scientific perspective, data requirements and computational complexity, predictive accuracy, and practical applicability in various geospatial contexts. The comparison was made based on the results of this study, literature review, and the authors' experiences. The results of the comparison are summarized in Table 7. Discussions of the comparison results for the approaches are provided in the following sections.

Figure 14. Landslide hazard mapping using the TRIGRS approach.

Methodological and scientific perspective

The comparative analysis highlights clear methodological contrasts among heuristic, statistical, and physically based approaches. AHP (AUC = 68.03%) is transparent and intuitive, relying on expert judgment to assign relative weights to conditioning factors such as slope, lithology, land cover, and drainage proximity. Its strength lies in its simplicity and ease of implementation, particularly where technical capacity or data availability is limited. However, its dependence on subjective decision-making reduces reproducibility, and its static assumption of factor importance constrains its ability to reflect dynamic processes that drive rainfall-induced landslides.

FR (AUC = 68.48%) incorporates landslide inventories to quantify statistical associations between conditioning factors and observed failures. This makes it more data-driven than AHP and less dependent on subjective weighting. Nevertheless, FR assumes linear proportionality between factor class frequency and landslide occurrence, which oversimplifies the complex, often nonlinear interactions that control slope stability. Additionally, its reliability is strongly tied to the quality and completeness of the landslide inventory, which can be a limitation in regions where inventories are sparse or inconsistent like Ardi watershed.

LR (AUC = 70.57%) extends beyond FR by handling multiple predictors simultaneously and producing coefficients that quantify their relative contributions. It assumes a linear relationship between predictors and the log-odds of landslide occurrence, which allows for straightforward interpretation but may limit its ability to capture nonlinear or threshold-based interactions (e.g. rainfall intensity or slope thresholds). LR is also sensitive to collinearity among predictors, requiring careful data preparation.

The Hybrid approach (AUC = 81.53%), which combines AHP, FR, and penalized logistic regression, offers an improved balance between interpretability and predictive strength. By integrating expert judgment, inventory-based ratios, and a penalized regression framework, the Hybrid reduces subjectivity, accounts for data-driven evidence, and minimizes the impact of collinearity. This integration provides more reliable susceptibility outcomes and demonstrates the potential of combining methods to overcome the weaknesses of standalone approaches.

In contrast, TRIGRS (AUC = 88.97%) achieved the highest scientific realism by explicitly simulating rainfall infiltration, suction dissipation, and factor of safety ($FS < 1$). Unlike empirical or statistical models, TRIGRS links rainfall forcing with geotechnical properties and hydrological responses, enabling event-based hazard modeling. This makes it uniquely capable of replicating the September 2020 landslide event in the Ardi Watershed, capturing both the timing and spatial extent of failures. Its physics-based foundation distinguishes it as the most process-consistent method, aligning closely with observed landslide triggers in the watershed.

These results indicate that while empirical and statistical models provide useful baseline susceptibility insights, process-based TRIGRS most accurately represents the physical mechanisms of rainfall-induced slope failures in the Ardi Watershed.

Data requirements and complexity

Data requirements varied substantially across the models, directly influencing their practicality and predictive performance. AHP required only conditioning factors, which are relatively easy to obtain from remote sensing and topographic datasets. This low data demand makes AHP suitable for data-scarce settings, but it comes at the cost of robustness and accuracy.

FR, in addition to conditioning factors, required a complete and accurate landslide inventory to establish statistical frequencies. In this study, inventories were validated with field investigation, served as the foundation for the analysis. This reliance on past events strengthens the empirical basis of FR but also introduces sensitivity to inventory quality. If the inventory is incomplete or biased toward accessible locations, the model's predictions will be skewed.

LR and the Hybrid demanded not only inventories but also balanced sampling between landslide and non-landslide locations. In this study, 20,000 data were used to address class imbalance, which increased computational effort but ensured greater statistical stability. The inclusion of penalized logistic regression

in the Hybrid further strengthened the modeling framework. Unlike standard LR, which can be distorted by multicollinearity and overfitting when predictors are correlated, penalized LR introduces a regularization term (L1, L2, or Elastic Net) into the estimation process. This penalty shrinks regression coefficients toward zero, reducing variance, stabilizing coefficient estimates, and ensuring that no single factor exerts disproportionate influence. In the Ardi watershed case, this regularization enhanced generalization and improved predictive reliability, as reflected in the Hybrid model's higher accuracy (AUC = 81.53%) compared to standalone AHP, FR, and LR. However, from a complexity perspective, penalized LR requires iterative optimization procedures and parameter tuning (e.g. selecting the penalty weight λ), making it more computationally demanding than AHP, FR, and LR, which rely on direct weights or frequency ratios. While this complexity increases runtime and requires careful preprocessing (balanced samples, scaling), it remains far less intensive than physically based models like TRIGRS. As such, the Hybrid with penalized LR represents a middle ground: more sophisticated and robust than empirical/statistical methods, yet still computationally feasible for regional-scale applications.

TRIGRS, however, was by far the most data-intensive. Its inputs included high-resolution DEM (5 m), hourly rainfall data from the September 8, 2020 storm, soil thickness from electrical resistivity surveys, and laboratory-derived geotechnical parameters such as hydraulic conductivity, soil-water characteristic curves, unit weight, cohesion, and friction angle. While this level of data preparation is resource-intensive, it enabled TRIGRS to directly simulate how rainfall infiltration translated into pore-pressure rise and slope failure.

In the Ardi Watershed, this trade-off was evident: empirical models such as AHP and FR were quicker to implement but offered only modest reliability, while LR provided moderate improvements through statistical rigor at the cost of greater data preparation and sensitivity to collinearity. The Hybrid with penalized LR further increased complexity by requiring balanced sampling and parameter tuning, yet it delivered stronger predictive stability. TRIGRS, despite being the most data- and computation-intensive, ultimately best captured the observed slope failure processes under intense rainfall.

Predictive accuracy

Model validation revealed distinct strengths and weaknesses across the five approaches. TRIGRS consistently outperformed all other methods, achieving the highest accuracy with AUC = 88.97%, Precision = 67%, TPR = 61%, FPR = 11%, and F1 = 64%. Its ability to reproduce both the spatial distribution and timing of the September 2020 landslides confirms its strength as an event-based hazard model and highlights the value of process-based approaches for rainfall-induced landslides.

Among the empirical methods, FR (AUC = 68.48%) slightly outperformed AHP (AUC = 68.03%), though both showed weak thresholded skill. FR obtained Precision = 41%, TPR = 29%, FPR = 15%, and F1 = 34%, while AHP produced Precision = 44%, TPR = 31%, FPR = 16%, and F1 = 36%. These results indicate that although both methods are useful for preliminary susceptibility mapping, they tend to miss many true landslide locations and generate a relatively high number of false positives.

LR achieved AUC = 70.57%, with Precision = 45%, TPR = 29%, FPR = 14%, and F1 = 36%. This shows a moderate improvement over AHP and FR, reflecting the advantages of a statistically based multivariate approach. However, its low TPR suggests that many actual landslides were not detected, while its assumption of a linear relationship between predictors and the log-odds of occurrence limited its flexibility in capturing complex factor interactions.

The Hybrid model (AHP + FR + penalty LR) delivered a notable boost in performance, reaching AUC = 81.53%, with Precision = 23%, TPR = 67%, FPR = 29%, and F1 = 34%. These values demonstrate that the Hybrid was more sensitive, capturing a larger proportion of actual landslides (high TPR), but at the expense of generating more false positives (low Precision, high FPR). While this reduces its suitability for real-time applications, it provides reliable coverage for regional-scale hazard planning where minimizing missed events is a priority.

These outcomes reflect the limitation of relying on a relatively small landslide inventory in the Ardi Watershed. With fewer true events available for calibration, empirical and statistical models tended to overgeneralize hazard zones, which inflated the number of false alarms and reduced precision. In contrast,

TRIGRS, being less dependent on inventory completeness, achieved both higher accuracy and lower false positives.

Strengths and limitations

In this study, each method demonstrated strengths that matched different practical needs. The AHP method provided a quick screening tool under data-poor conditions, but its reliance on expert judgment limited objectivity and reduced accuracy. The FR method was simple to apply and transparent, however, its assumption of equal weighting across all factors did not capture the specific influences of local geology, slope, and land use, leading to low sensitivity and false alarms. The LR model supported multivariate analysis and probability-based susceptibility mapping, but its performance depended heavily on balanced sampling and the quality of the inventory, resulting in low recall (TPR) and moderate false positives. The AHP + FR + penalty LR model significantly improved mapping accuracy by combining expert insight, inventory evidence, and statistical refinement, making it practical for regional-scale applications where inventories are incomplete but expert knowledge exists. Finally, the TRIGRS model delivered the most accurate and realistic results by simulating rainfall infiltration and slope instability, successfully reproducing the September 2020 landslide event. However, its extensive data and computational requirements restricted its scalability for larger-area hazard assessment.

Conclusions and recommendations

This study provides a comprehensive comparison of five landslide hazard mapping techniques, including the AHP, FR, LR, AHP + FR + Penalty LR, and TRIGRS methods, applied to the Ardi Watershed study site in northern Thailand. The following findings and recommendations are provided based on the results of the study, literature review, and the Authors' experience.

- Among the evaluated methods, the TRIGRS method achieved the highest accuracy (AUC = 88.97%) due to its physically based rainfall infiltration and slope stability modeling. Its ability to simulate the timing and progression of landslides makes it ideal for site-specific applications, such as infrastructure planning and early warning systems. However, its high data and computational demands may limit its use in large-scale or data-scarce areas. In contrast, the AHP and FR methods are more accessible for preliminary assessments. The AHP method is suitable for data-poor regions but is subjective, while the FR method is simple and data-driven but assumes equal factor importance. The AHP + FR + LR hybrid significantly improved accuracy (AUC = 81.53%) by combining expert judgment with empirical data, and analyze them with multivariate model. The LR and hybrid methods also showed moderate performance, offering a statistically sound approach but requiring careful data preparation.
- In this study, the AHP + FR + LR hybrid method was employed to enhance the accuracy of landslide hazard mapping by integrating the strengths of expert-driven and data-driven approaches. The AHP method provided a structured approach for expert judgment to assign relative importance to conditioning factors, while the FR method contributed objective, inventory-based susceptibility scores for non-continuous factors. By combining these models, the AHP + FR + Penalty LR hybrid model addressed each of its limitations. This integration not only improved the mapping process but also resulted in significantly higher predictive accuracy (AUC = 81.53%) compared to the standalone AHP (68.03%) and FR (68.48%) models. The hybrid approach proved to be both efficient and practical, especially in contexts where partial inventory data and expert knowledge are available. These findings demonstrate that the use of combination methods can substantially improve the reliability of hazard assessments and contribute to more informed risk management and mitigation planning.
- An essential contribution of this study was integrating rainfall intensity as a temporal triggering factor. Rainfall classification has a significant influence on landslide hazard assessment outcomes. The study evaluated fixed interval classifications (10 mm and 40 mm), K-means clustering, and logistic regression-based classification. The LR classification enhances mapping accuracy by assigning distinct

rainfall scores to each pixel, unlike other classification methods that apply uniform scores across zones. Results confirmed that the method of rainfall categorization directly affects the spatial distribution of hazard zones, underscoring the importance of selecting context-appropriate classification schemes when modeling rainfall-induced landslide hazard map.

- To further enhance the accuracy of hazard maps, this study tested three landslide hazard index (LHI) zonation methods: Geometrical Interval (GI), Quantile (QT), and Natural Breaks (NB). Each method is based on a different theoretical background, resulting in varying hazard zones. Therefore, to assess the mapping accuracy, it is essential to consider the differences in these zonation methods.
- Based on the results of this study, the AHP method is recommended for rapid assessments in data-limited environments where expert input is available. The FR method is suitable for quick susceptibility mapping in areas with reliable landslide inventories. The LR method is best applied in research settings where variable interactions are of interest and balanced data can be ensured. The AHP + FR + Penalty LR hybrid method provides an effective balance between expert judgment and data-driven analysis, making it a practical option for moderate-scale studies. The TRIGRS method is ideal for detailed, site-specific applications such as infrastructure planning, early warning systems, and disaster risk reduction strategies where high-resolution data and accurate predictions are essential. These recommendations are also summarized in [Table 7](#).

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Author contributions

CRediT: **Terdkiad Nontapot**: conceptualization, data collection, data analysis, and writing original draft preparation; **Kuo Chieh Chao**: conceptualization, data analysis, guidance, manuscript review and editing, supervision, and funding acquisition. Both authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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